

SingMaster: an Intelligent Mobile Game for Teaching Singing

Georgi Dzhambazov¹, Kamen Goranchev², Xavier Serra¹

¹Music Technology Group, Universitat Pompeu Fabra, Barcelona, Spain

²Cygenocode, Vienna, Austria

Music
Technology
Group

cygenocode

contact: georgi.dzhambazov@upf.edu

an interactive game with visual feedback for singing wannabes

- Intuitive layout
- Two modes: Exercises and Songs
- Visual feedback of sung melody

Melody extraction technology [1]

Exercises mode

Songs mode

References

[1] Salomon J. and Gómez, E Melody extraction from polyphonic music signals using pitch contour characteristics. IEEE TSALP, 20(6):1759–1770, 2012.

<https://www.facebook.com/SINGmasterapp/>

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=bg.singmaster.gui&hl=en>